

GOMUTRA: A PANACEA FOR ALL DISEASES

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Abstract:

Cow is cited as Aditi (Mother of all Gods) in Ancient Hindi texts. In Artharaveda, Cow is said as adobe of 33Cr Hindu deities. Cow Urine (CU); the liquid metabolic excretion of Cow, is treated as sacred and pious in India. CU has diversified uses. It is used in raw and refined forms. Research reveals that CU distillate (CUD) is even more effective in therapeutic applications. CUD; Gomutra Ark or Kamdhenu Ark, was used since ancient times in Indian, Chinese and Egyptian civilizations. CU is also used in Myanmar, Nepal, Nigeria and Zimbabwe as curator [1,2]. Variants of CU are also sold in departmental stores in America, Britain, Canada, Germany and India. Several Cow Urine Concoctions (CUC) serve as curative agents against deadly ailments. Being easily available, having long shelf life and economically cheaper; Gomutra variants are now becoming alternative medicines against innumerable diseases [3-6].

Biochemical composition of CU makes it perfect supplement against various disorders. CU of milking Cow contains 95% Water, 2.5% Urea and 2.5% Enzymes, Hormones, Minerals and Salts. pH of fresh CU ranges from 7.27 to 8.74. CU from a healthy Cow is pale yellow colored. Traces of Gold are found in CU of Gir Cows. Gold ions are generated when blood vessels of Cow hump comes in contact with sunrays. On an average about 18 Lit/Day of CU can be collected from an Indian Cow. Branded CUD can be easily obtained @ of Rs 250/500 ml in India.

Advances on Gomutra are so prominent that America granted US Patent No: 6410059 and No: 6896907 for the medicinal ability of CU, especially as Anticancer, Antifungal, Antibiotic and Bioenhancer agent [16]. Present text is an overview of applications of Gomutra, particularly therapeutic applications.

Keywords: Cow Urine, Cow Urine Concoction, Cow Urine Distillate, Gomutra

1. Introduction:

Principal deities, Brahma, Vishnu and Mahesh treated Cow as most sacred animal on earth. According to Vedas; Ancient Indian Text, one can attain Moksha (Salvation) by serving and worshiping Cow. 33 Cr Hindu deities are believed to reside in Cow and is thus worshipped as most sacred and pious creature on earth. Five bi-products of Cow namely; CU (Gomutra), Cow dung (Gomaya), Cow milk (Godugdha), Cow curd (Godadhi) and Cow Ghee (Goghrit) collectively known as Panchgavya have immense utility value. Amongst constituents of Panchgavya, the Gomutra is cheapest and easily available, and has enormous therapeutic applications [7].

CU has zero percent glucose, hemoglobin and protein. It contains 15 ul/lit of Leucocyte, 23-28ml/Kg/Day of Nitrogen and 40-45 ml/Kg/Day of Total Nitrogen. Specific gravity varies between 1.025-1.045. The pH value of CU of healthy Cow ranges from 7.27-8.74. CU contains 2.5% by weight of Urea. CU contains 2.5% Enzymes, Hormones, Minerals and Salts. CU is a rich and natural source of Copper, Sulphur, Iron, Phosphorus, Potassium, Sodium, Manganese, Calcium and Gold. CU contains many acids like, Uric acid, Carbolic acid, Hippuric acid, Benzoic acid, Aromatic Hydroxy

acid and amino acid. Gomutra is a cheapest source of multi Vitamins as it contains Vitamin-A, B, C, D, and E. Gomutra also contains Lactate, Amylase, Acid Phosphotase and Alkaline Phosphotase. Deficiency and excess of these essential elements in human body may cause disorders. However, CU treatment can act as Balancer, Bioenhancer, antibiotic, antifungal and anticancer agent against bodily disorders [8,9].

According to Cow Urine Treatment Research Centre (CUTRC), Indore, Gomutra is capable of curing AIDS, Acidity, Arthritis, Asthma, Blood pressure, Bronchitis, Blockage in arteries, Cancer, Constipation, Diabetes, Eczema, Ear and nose problems, Fits, Gynecological problems, Heart attack, Leprosy, Migraine, Piles, Psoriasis, Prostrate, Thyroid etc. All India Hindu Union (AIHU) believes, CU develop antibodies against COVID-19 pathogens. Hindu Group offers CU in a bid to ward off Coronavirus [10-15]].

Apart from medicinal uses, CU is also used as Religious rituals performer, Organic manure, Floor cleanser and Diesel emulsifier.

GOMUTRA IN HINDU MYTHOLOGY

Gomutra is well described in several ancient holy text like Ayurveda, Atharvaveda, Amritsagar, Bhavprakash, Charak Samhita, Rajni Ghuntu, Manu Smariti, Sushruta Samhita, Vridhabhagabhatt etc. CU was a symbol of sanctity and Aushadhi for many ailments. Many traditional Vidhis of curing Roga are described in these scriptures.

In the ancient holy book Dammar Tantra, Lord Shiva explained Advantages of Gomutra to Mother Parvati. CU was termed as Shivambu meaning Water of Shiva. In Damaar Tantra healing by Self Urine Therapy is described as Shivambukalpa Vidhi. Urine is also described in Bhavprakash as Vishaghna (Anti Toxicant) meaning killer of all poisons. In Charak Samhita and Sushrut Samhita and Ashtanga Hridaya, Gomutra is described as Rasayana (Rejuvenater) meaning energy booster for all. The reference of Urine Therapy is also mentioned in Ayurvedic literature. All the disorders due to Kaphaja and Vataja can be cured by Gomutra [13].

TRADITIONAL THERAPEUTIC APPLICATIONS OF GOMUTRA

CU, CUCs and CUDs are in use since ancient times . Fresh CU was used within 3-6 hours, CUD was used upto 6-8 months and CUD could be used in 5-6 years. Several diseases were cured using appropriate variant of Gomutra. Panchgavya Chikitsa (Medical science based on five components of Panchgavya) was acceptable in society as remedy for all bodily disorders since Vedic and Prevedic era [17,18]. Few diseases with their adjuvants of CU are mentioned below:

Disease	Adjuvants of CU
• Anemia	1. Dugdha, Triphala 2. Dugdha, Loh Bhasma
• Epilepsy	Nimbuchal
• Fever	Curd, Ghee, Pepper
• Leprosy	Dhruhardi
• Chronic Leprosy	Vasaka and Kaner leaves, Kuraila and Neem bark
• Deformation in Leprosy	Dharuhardi, Nimbuchal
• Worm Infestation	Neem leaves

The CUC prepared from the leaves of Tobacco, Garlic and Basil, Lemon juice, Rock salt and onion was used to control depression of nervous system, respiration, cardiovascular system and Hyperglycemia in ancient China, Egypt, India and most popularly in Yoruba community of Nigeria. In Zimbabwe, CU is traditionally

used in controlling Fusarium Bark Disease (FBD), an endemic in the coffee growing regions [19]. In ancient India, CUC of Dhatura (Dhatura Metel), Guggul (Comnifera Mukul), Loha (Fe) and Bhalataka (Semecorpus Anacardium) was used in Detoxification of Silver (Ag) and Aconite (Aconitum Napellus).

BIOCHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF CU

Analytical studies of CU has shown that CU contains 95% Water, 2.5% Urea and 2.5% Enzymes, Hormones, Minerals and various salts. CU doesn't contain Protein, Glucose and Hemoglobin [21-27]. Various constituents of CU are given below:

- Water (H₂O): Helps in maintaining body temperature and fluidity of blood.
- Urea (CONH₂): Affects formation and removal of urine.
- Enzymes: Lactase, Phosphatase and Urease are found in CU. These Enzymes produce active digestive juices and increase immunity.
- Minerals: They increase immunity against pathogens.
- Salts: Chlorides, Phosphates and Carbonates are found in CU. Presence of salts decreases acidic contents of blood.
- Vitamins (A, B, C, D, E): They provide energy. Vitamin B is essential for active energetic life, saves from nervousness, thirst and fatigue.
- Creatinine: Act as germicide.
- Lactose (C₆H₁₂O₆): Removes thirst and nervousness, strengthens heart and gives satisfaction.
- Aurum Hydroxide (AuOH): Highly Antibiotic and Anti Toxicant, Germicidal and Immunity booster.
- Uric acid (C₅H₄N₄O₃): Removes heart swelling or inflammation and is Diuretic therefore remove toxins.
- Carbolic acid (HCOOH): Protects against decay due to gangrene. It is Germicidal.
- Hippuric acid (C₉H₉NO₃): Removes toxins through urine.
- Nitrogen (N₂): Removes blood impurities. Natural Stimulant of urinary track, activates kidney and is Diuretic.
- Ammonia (NH₃): Stabilize bile, mucus and air of body, and formation of blood.
- Sulphur (S): Supports motion in large intestine. Cleanses bloat.

- Phosphorous (P): Helps in removing Calcium oxalate stones from urinary track.
- Potassium (K): Cures hereditary rheumatism, increases appetite, removes muscular weakness and laziness.
- Calcium (Ca): Strengthen skeletal and improves bone formation.
- Manganese (Mg): Stops growth of germs.
- Copper (Cu): Controls obesity.
- Iron (Fe): Helps in production of RBC and hemoglobin.
- Gold (Au): Improves vitality and longevity.

MECHANISM OF THERAPEUTIC ACTIVITY OF CU

Gomutra is described in Ayurveda, Ashtanga Sangraha and Sushruta Samhita as Bioenhancer (Which increases Biological activity of reagent). CUD being more effective than CU is used as Bioenhancer. It increases the activity of Gonadotropin Releasing Hormone (GnRH) conjugative with Zinc and Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA). CUD increases Bio Enhancing Activity (BEA) for Rifampicin (Premium medicine for Tuberculosis). It enhances action against E-Coli and Gram Positive Bacteria (GPB). CUD enhances the transport of Antibiotics like Ampicillin, Rifampicin and Tetracycline, across the gut wall and artificial membranes. Transport enhancement may vary 2-7 fold. Conjugate base has ill effects on menstrual cycle of females. It also has injurious effect on female reproductive hormones. Gomutra Ark act as a Bioenhancer of immunization efficacy to modulate deleterious effects of conjugate base [21-27].

CU exhibits Antitoxic activity against Cadmium Chloride ($CdCl_2$) and can be used as Bioenhancer for Zinc (Zn) and Zinc Sulphate ($ZnSO_4$). Fertility rate, Lactation Indices and Fertility Index increase when treated with CU in presence of $CdCl_2$.

CU can modulate several bodily functions. It augments antibody titers and lymphocyte blastogenesis. It augments secretion of interleukin phagocytic activity of macrophages and is helpful in prevention and control of infections.

Anticancer characteristic of CU is due to uric acid's antioxidant ability and allantoin. Immunity increases due to Swarn Kshar ($AuOH$) and wound healing is faster due to allantoin. Antimicrobial and Germicidal effects of CU are due to the presence of Swarn Kshar, Urea, Creatinine, Carbolic acid ($HCOOH$), Phenols, Calcium (Ca) and Manganese (Mn). Nitrogen acts as Renal Stimulant and maintains Renal health. Urinary components are responsible for Diuretic activity. Hippuric acid, Nitrogen, Phosphates and Uric acid also act as Diuretic agents. Copper ions act as Anti Obesity agent and Calcium (Ca) strengthens skeletal and formation of bones. Copper act as Antidote for many toxicants.

Cardiovascular activity is improved by Kallikrein (Vasodulator). The enzyme Urkinase act as a Fibrinolytic agent. Integrity of blood vessels is maintained by Ammonia (NH_3). Iron (Fe) and Erythroprotein maintain hemoglobin levels. Calcium, Nitrogen, Sodium and Sulphur act as blood purifiers.

Presence of amino acids and urinary peptides may enhance the bactericidal effect by increasing the bacterial cell surface hydrophobicity. In photo activated CU few volatile organic and inorganic compounds are formed, making photo activated urine more active than fresh CU. Enhancement of Bactericidal effect may be due to decrease in pH, presence of dimethylamine, chloride and inorganic phosphorus. Bactericidal activity may also be attributed to increase in amines and ketones, during photo activation period.

ADDITIONAL APPLICATIONS OF CU

In addition to Therapeutic applications, CU has potential of other applications as mentioned below [28-30]:

- Emulsified Diesel: CU is used in production of CU emulsified diesel for Compression Ignition (C.I) engine. Such diesel reduces carbon emissions and improves C.I engine efficiency.
- Floor Cleanser: Germicidal properties of CU are utilized as floor cleanser. Holy Cow Foundation markets Gounyle as floor cleaning fluid. In many Government offices (Ministry of Environment) Gounyle is used in place of Phenyle. A plant in Rajasthan produces Gocleaner.
- Green Manure: Gomutra has all the essential ingredients like Urea, Minerals and Enzymes, required for enrichment of soil. CU in solo or with adjuvants; Cow dung (Gomaya), Jaggery, Pulse flour and Rhizosphere soil is used in Organic Farming instead of synthetic fertilizers. Product is known as Jeevmurtha.
- Religious Rituals: In many traditional societies, sprinkling of Gomutra is said to have spiritual cleaning effect while performing religious rituals.
- Plant Growth Enhancer: CU treated plants of Bhindi and Methi shew remarkable growth against fungal infection. Gomutra exhibits antifungal activity against Fusarium Oxysporum, Rhizotonia Solani and Sclerotium Rolfish fungi on plants of Bhindi and Methi [20].

CONCLUSION

CU or Gomutra is believed to be panacea medicine for all diseases. CU Concoctions and Distillates are used in countries like America, Britain, China, Egypt, Germany, India, Myammar, Nepal, Nigeria and Zimbabwe as Natural Antibiotic, Antifungal, Anticancer,

Bioenhancer and Green Manure agent. CUD or Gomutra Ark/ Kamdhenu Ark is more effective in therapeutic applications as compared to CU.

In India CUTRC is promoting research on CU. Still in many countries, consumption of animal urine is felt disgusting. Although ancient Indian scriptures report importance of Gomutra in medicinal field but folks require more scientifically proved data for acceptance of CU in Therapeutic applications.

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